

Research on Gesture Based on GA – SVM

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Abstract: Surface electromyography (sEMG) is a kind of weak electrical signal generated by muscle activity, which contains information of gesture and is widely used in prosthetic control, rehabilitation and medical treatment. The difference between different motion patterns can be reflected by the different sEMG characteristics, so the recognition of human motion can be studied. Four time-domain features including absolute mean value, waveform length, zero-crossing number and root mean square value were extracted from the double Myo arm-ring data set in Ninapro benchmark database. Classification and identification were performed by using the Support Vector Machine (SVM) optimized by Genetic Algorithms (GA). Experimental results showed that the optimized SVM classification had a better effect.

Keywords: surface electromyography; genetic algorithms; support vector machine

I. INTRODUCTION

With the continuous development of science and technology, intelligent technologies such as intelligent robots will be more and more closely connected with people. However, the previous human-machine interaction is not conducive to the communication and exchange between humans and robots, so people need to seek new technologies to solve this problem. Modern human interaction technology requires robots to passively accept human's instructions and actively understand human's behavior intention, thus derives a new type of human interaction mode based on bioelectrical signals [1].

When the body moves, the corresponding limbs will produce different types and sizes of bioelectrical signals, which can well reflect the intention of people and have good development value. sEMG signals are widely developed because they are easy to collect and contain abundant information.

At present, sEMG are mainly applied in interpersonal interaction, biofeedback and functional electrical stimulation[2]. Domestic researches include: Xu Zhang et al, university of science and technology of China, developed a real-time interactive system of human motion based on sEMG signal[3], and Shanghai jiaotong university applied near-infrared spectrum to control the EMG prosthetic hand[4]. Related studies abroad include: the German aerospace center has developed the multi-

degree of freedom underactuated prosthetic hand DRL, which is not only a powerful and position sensor, but also a torque sensor and potentiometer in each joint. It can grasp objects of different shapes and weights by controlling the fake hand through sEMG[5].

In this paper, four time-domain features of sEMG are extracted, and six gestures are recognized by an optimized SVM classifier.

II. GESTURE RECOGNITION SYSTEM DESIGN

In this paper, the design of recognition system mainly consists of three steps: active segment detection, feature extraction and gesture recognition, as shown in Fig.1. Then, the characteristic parameters extracted are simulated by MATLAB software, and the rationality of the identification system is judged according to the classification results.

Fig.1 gesture recognition system

A. Data Source

The data of the simulation experiment in this paper are from the double Myo armband data set in Ninapro

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benchmark database. This data set selects the Myo armband produced by a Canadian start-up company to collect the sEMG generated when the tester moves through the armband. In the heart of the acquisition process two Myo armband worn on the forearm of the tester, cuddled up together two arm rings, one of the upper arm ring close to the elbow, and armband first electrode on the humerus joints, the lower hand ring close to the hand, and relative to the upper hand rings tilted 22.5 degrees, to fill the upper hand ring spacing between electrodes [6], as shown in Fig.2.

Fig.2 schematic diagram of arm ring wearing

In the database, 10 healthy people were randomly selected as testers, who were defined to perform a variety of gestures, including 12 finger movements, 17 equally spaced wrist hand movements, and 23 grasping movements, each of which was completed by the right hand of the tester. In view of the validity of the experimental data, each tester was required to repeat the same action for 6 times, each gesture takes 5 seconds, and the tester was given a rest for 3 seconds between each action. In this paper, 6 kinds of finger movement data are selected for experimental simulation, which are Index flexion, Index extension, Middle flexion, Middle extension, Ring flexion, and Ring extension respectively. As shown in Fig.3, Rest is the gesture during Rest time.

B. Signal Processing

Myo has removed 50hz power frequency interference from the collected sEMG, so the experimental data are no longer filtered in this paper. The data from the two Myo armbands were recorded separately and merged afterwards on a timestamp basis. All the data streams were finally over-sampled to the frequency of the fastest device using linear interpolation [6].

Fig.3 schematic diagram of gestures

C. Moving Segment Detection

Because each perform a gestures corresponding to muscles through the process of resting - contraction - resting, but when resting the electromyographic signal is not necessary for the experiment, it is necessary to extract motion range from continuous sEMG, namely active period of the signal, the success of the activities section of the test or not become a prerequisite for the feature extraction and classification recognition[7]. Considering the convenience and real-time performance of the experiment, this paper uses the combination of moving average method and threshold method to judge the active segment. Moving average method is a simple finite impulse response filter, which has the ability to predict time series signals smoothly. It adopts fixed moving window to pass through and calculate the average value of sequence signals containing the length of the window successively, so as to reflect the long-term change trend of signals[8].

(1) Firstly, the mean of the difference sum of squares of sEMG signal sequence $S_t(i)$ of each channel is calculated to obtain the instantaneous average energy $S_{aver}(i)$ of signal, where N is the total number of channels of Myo armband, i is the label of the current signal sequence, and the value range of t is $1 \leq t \leq N$, as shown in equation (1).

$$S_{aver}(i) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N [S_t(i+1) - S_t(i)]^2 \quad (1)$$

(2) Take the moving window with a fixed window length of $L=128$ and calculate the average of the instantaneous energy in the window length in turn according to equation (2).

$$S_{jz}(i) = \frac{1}{L} \sum_{j=i}^{i+L-1} S_{aver}(j) \quad (2)$$

(3) As shown in equation (3), signal points larger than the threshold are reserved, and signal points lower than the threshold are set to zero. Based on this, the starting and ending points of the active segment are determined, and the active segment shorter than the window length is discarded as a judgment error.

$$S_{rec}(i) = \begin{cases} S_{jz}(i) & \text{if } S_{jz}(i) \geq \text{Threshold} \\ 0 & \text{if } S_{jz}(i) \leq \text{Threshold} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

D. Feature Extraction

Feature extraction is an important means to dig out the hidden useful information in sEMG and eliminate redundant parts and interference. A good set of feature vectors can greatly improve the success rate of action classification, which is the premise and key of sEMG action pattern recognition[9]. At present, the feature extraction methods of sEMG are mainly divided into three categories: time-domain feature, frequency domain feature and time-frequency domain feature.

Time domain special do not need any transformation of the electromyographic signal extraction, instead it can be directly calculated by original electromyographic signal time series[10], the time domain features with low complexity and stable performance are selected in this paper.

(1) The mathematical expression of Mean Absolute Value (MAV) is:

$$MAV = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |x(i)| \quad (4)$$

(2) Waveform Length (WL) is the electromyographic signal complexity measure[11], on the meaning of time electrical Waveform of accumulative total Length, its expression is:

$$WL = \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} |x(i+1) - x(i)| \quad (5)$$

(3) Zero Crossing (ZC) is a statistic of the number of times that sEMG cross the Zero amplitude value. In order to avoid the fluctuation of low voltage, threshold conditions can be applied to the calculation, which can be expressed as:

$$\begin{cases} ZC = \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} f_i \\ f_i = \begin{cases} 1 & x_i x_{i+1} < 0, |x_k - x_{k+1}| > YZ \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

(4) Root Mean Square (RMS) is based on the assumption that the sEMG generated during muscle contraction are gauss random process with amplitude modulation, which is closely related to the fatigue free constant force contraction of muscles. Its mathematical expression is:

$$RMS = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N x^2(i)} \quad (7)$$

In the process of experiment, 4 time domain features of a channel are extracted, which are 64 dimensional feature parameters in total.

E. Support Vector Machine Classifier

Pattern classification refers to the process of classifying input eigenvectors by classifier. The classifier chosen in this paper is support vector machine (SVM). Its basic principle is: the binary classification problems of non-linear feature mapped to high-dimensional space, makes the nonlinear characteristics in high dimensional space linear separable, and then in the high-dimensional space build classification hyperplane to sample [12]. Fig.4.1 is the schematic diagram of SVM. There are two different kinds of samples, and multiple lines can separate the two kinds of coordinates. But is there an optimal solution? When the distance between the dividing line and two types of samples is larger, the training probability of training samples into another type will be smaller in the training process of SVM classifier, so that the classification results obtained in the test part of SVM will be better and the classification accuracy will be higher. Therefore, the goal is to find a dividing line that is as far away from all sample points as possible, that is, the optimal hyperplane, as shown in Fig. 4.2.

Fig.4.1 schematic

diagram of SVM

It is assumed that the hyperplane is $f(x)$, whose expression is shown in equation (8) :

$$f(x) = w * x + b \quad (8)$$

δ_i is defined as the geometric distance from the eigenvector x_i to the hyperplane, as shown in equation (9) :

$$\delta_i = \frac{1}{\|w\|} |f(x_i)| \quad (9)$$

In the formula, $\|w\|$ is the 2-norm of w .

In order to obtain the maximum geometric interval, $\|w\|$ is required to be the minimum. Now the minimum $\|w\|$ is defined as $\min \frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2$. Due to the existence of constraint conditions, an optimization function with constraints is obtained:

$$\begin{cases} \min \frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2 \\ \text{subject to } y_i(w * x + b) - 1 \geq 0 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

The above problem can be converted into an unconstrained function by introducing Lagrange operator:

$$L(w, b, a) = \frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2 - \sum_{i=1}^m \alpha_i (y_i(w * x_i + b) - 1) \quad (11)$$

Where m is the number of training samples.

After Lagrange multiplier is introduced, the optimization function is converted to:

$$\min(w, b) \max(\alpha_i \geq 0) L(w, b, a) \quad (12)$$

This optimization function satisfies the KKT (Karush Kuhn Tucher) condition and converts the optimization problem into an equivalent dual problem to be solved by Lagrange duality. According to the dual complementarity in KKT conditions, there are:

Fig.4.2 optimal hyperplane in SVM

$$a_i (y_i (w * x + b)) = 0 \quad (13)$$

If $a_i > 0$, we have $y_i(w * x + b) = 1$, which is the point on the support vector, and if $a_i = 0$, we have $y_i(w * x + b) \geq 1$, which is the sample has been classified exactly or on the support vector.

III. OPTIMAL DESIGN OF SUPPORT VECTOR MACHINE CLASSIFIER

Since the classification results of SVM classifiers are greatly affected by penalty parameters C and kernel function parameters g , this paper uses the global optimization capability of Genetic Algorithms (GA) to optimize the selection process of penalty parameters C and kernel function parameters g in SVM, so as to improve the classification effect of SVM.

A. Genetic algorithms

Genetic algorithm is a new parallel search optimization algorithm, which can cover all the possibilities of the problem to be solved. Its principle is to encode samples according to chromosomes, determine fitness, and then carry out selection, crossover, mutation and other genetic operations on genetic operators [13]. The principle involved are as follows [14] :

(1)Chromosome coding. Chromosome coding is an individual coding method, which can transform the solution of the original problem into the range that can be handled by genetic algorithm. In coding, binary method is often used to encode the possible solution of the problem.

(2)Fitness function. In genetic algorithms, individual fitness is often used to describe individual performance, and the algorithm selects individuals according to their fitness. The solution of fitness function needs to combine the objective function and constraint conditions with appropriate penalty function to establish an unconstrained optimization objective function and carry out corresponding transformation operation, so as to obtain the correct fitness function.

(3)Genetic operations and genetic operators. Genetic operation refers to the selection, crossover and mutation of individuals by genetic algorithm through genetic operator to judge the continuation of downward inheritance or elimination of individuals and determine the individual and specific size of the population of descendants. The main operations include: selection operation, crossover operation, mutation operation.

(4)Parameter setting. In the calculation of genetic algorithm, initialization parameters should be set first, including: population size M, the general value range is [20-100];The maximum genetic algebra T is generally [10-100], crossover probability p_c and mutation probability p_m ,The value ranges of the two are [0.5-1.0] and [0-0.05].

B. Genetic Algorithms – Support Vector Machine Classifier

Fig.5 is a flow chart of GA optimization SVM.

The steps of genetic algorithm in SVM optimization are as follows:

(1)In the process of chromosome coding to generate the initial population, the binary method is adopted in this paper to encode the penalty parameter C and kernel function parameter g, that is, to encode the two

parameters into binary strings to form the initial population.

(2)In the calculation of individual fitness, in order to verify the accuracy of the experimental results, the recognition rate of the training set in the Cross Validation of 5 was selected as the fitness value in this paper, so as to retain the reproducibility of the experimental process and reduce the interference of random factors.

(3)In the aspect of crossover operation, this paper adopts single point crossover. The crossover probability was set to p_c , and the crossover points were randomly determined among the paired parental individuals, and some genes of the paired individuals were exchanged at the crossover points. In terms of mutation operation, loci that need to be mutated are randomly determined, and the mutation operation is conducted by taking the mutation probability p_m and inverting the gene value bit by bit.

(4) This paper sets the termination condition as the maximum genetic algebra.

IV. Analysis of experimental results

A. Experimental Results of Moving Segment Detection

In accordance with section 1.3 of the steps to look for the activities of the action, Fig.6 for the average energy in moving window multi-channel sEMG, through selecting proper threshold, the average energy is less than the threshold and part length less than the threshold value of the zero, as shown in Fig.7, the figure of 72 active segment corresponds to each repeat 6 times of 12 kinds of action, this article selects the first 36 activity, namely of 6 different gestures as experimental objects.

Fig.6 Schematic diagram of sEMG energy mean

Fig.7 Schematic diagram of active segment interval

B. Experimental Results of Action Classification

The feature parameters extracted in accordance with the steps in section 1.4 are put into classifier. In the SVM classifier, when the training set data is 9, the accuracy rate is only 79.6%, as shown in Fig.8, while when the number of test set data is 9, the accuracy rate of GA-SVM classifier can reach 83.3%, as shown in Fig.9. Category tag 1 is Index flexion, category tag 2 is Index extension, category tag 3 is Middle flexion, category tag 4 is Middle extension, category tag 5 is Ring flexion, and category tag 6 is Ring extension. The iterative process of genetic algorithm is shown in Fig.10.

Fig.8 SVM classification results with training set data of 9

Fig.9 GA-SVM classification results with training set data of 9

Fig. 10 fitness curve of GA

When the number of training set data is 12, the accuracy rate of SVM classifier is 80.5% and that of GA-SVM classifier is 91.7%, respectively, as shown in

Fig.11 and Fig.12. The iterative process of genetic algorithm is shown in Fig.13.

Fig.11 SVM classification results with training set data quantity of 12

Fig.12 GA-SVM classification results with 12 training set data

Fig.13 fitness curve of GA

When the number of training set data is 15, the accuracy rate of SVM classifier is 88.8%, and that of GA-SVM classifier is 94.4%, respectively, as shown in Fig.14 and Fig.15. The iterative process of genetic algorithm is shown in Fig.16.

Fig.14 SVM classification results with training set data quantity of 15

Fig.15 GA-SVM classification results with training set data quantity of 15

Fig.16 fitness curve of GA

As shown in Fig.17, the recognition rate of GA-SVM is higher than that of SVM when the data of the three training sessions are all different. The average recognition rate of SVM is 83%, and the average recognition rate of GA-SVM can reach 90%. On the whole, when the training set data are different, the legacy algorithm optimizes the punishment parameters C and kernel function g of SVM, and improves the classification accuracy. The horizontal coordinate in the figure represents the number of data in the training set as 9, 12 and 15 respectively.

Fig.17 comparison of classification results between GA-SVM and SVM

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper chooses a Ninapro benchmark database double MYO armband data set three different test data, extracting the time domain characteristics of four different: the mean absolute, the number of passing zero, the wave length and root mean square, through genetic algorithm (GA) optimize the support vector machine (SVM), compared with SVM and GA - SVM classification as a result, the optimized SVM classification results are improved. However, the data selected in this paper are few, and the diversity of samples and actions are not fully considered. These problems need to be solved in the later work.

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